

DAISY DUB - THE PLAYABLE DELAY

Rasmus KJÆRBO¹

¹*Sound & Music Computing, Aalborg University, DK*

²*Rumkraft Aps, Copenhagen, Denmark*

ABSTRACT

The surge of advanced microcontrollers allowing for real-time processing of audio has taken the DIY world of instrument and effect builders by storm. This project utilises the Daisy Seed barebone platform from ElectroSmith to implement a high definition playable musical delay for dub mixing and live performance. An important aspect of the platform is the capability to execute C++ code with extremely low latency at 24-bit 96kHz audio quality, comparable to state of the art delays like the contemporary and widely used El Capistan by Strymon Engineering. A second aspect of the project seeks to replicate the specific character and playability of vintage delay Roland SDE-2500 - one of dub pioneer King Tubby's favourites. Finally, the project explores rapid prototyping of real-time audio effects and sound generation with Max and Gen by Cycling74 and the translation to executable and embeddable Daisy Seed code with the Max object, Oopsy by ElectroSmith. Evaluation, design, and implementation was conducted alongside a series of qualitative interviews with avid music producers, sound engineers and live performers with expertise in delays, sound design, and dub mixing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Music producers, sound designers, audio effect developers, DSP programmers, musicians, sound-, mixing- and mastering engineers, and live performers all utilize delay lines. Whether for inspiring and driving polyrhythms generated by the interplay of freely timed or synced repetitions of audio or for swelling sound effects during a live performance, working with analog or digital audio will most surely take your journey past a plethora of delay lines.

Many versions of the delay effect exist, each with its own unique take on controlling and bending time. In this project, I construct the Daisy Dub Delay (see fig. 1) a digitally controlled, high definition delay with design and sound characteristics of the dub era in the 60s and 70s Jamaica and United Kingdom. In said era, dub producers and sound engineers usually worked as electrical engineers, constructing their own unique sound effects in order to stand out and champion the record and sound system scene [1]. The delays from the 60s and 70s were predominantly analog, rack mounted and had few knobs and

Figure 1. Daisy Dub Delay - <https://youtu.be/fcGmwTvWMJk>

buttons along with simple LCD displays. Advanced delays of that time offered layers of menu diving - great for sound design, but hard for live manipulation of parameters. Lastly, you still needed to patch delays in series to other effects to achieve the out-of-this-World soundscapes, as dub music often explores.

The design goal of this project is to offer simplified access to direct controls of the delay line, with a limited but expressive amount of extra sound design options accessed via a display and a rotary push encoder. Concealing the majority of parameters in a simple and accessible menu system maximizes playability without compromising sound design possibilities.

1.1 State of the art

1.1.1 El Capistan by Strymon Engineering - released 2010

El Capistan is a 24-bit 96kHz delay with various types of modulation, input stage filter, filter in feedback path, and an algorithmic spring reverb. A go-to delay for musicians and dub mixers alike. The form factor is great, but interaction with the unit is limited to only five knobs, two three-way switches, and two stomp buttons (bypass and tap tempo) (see fig. 2). One particular thing about El Capistan is the MODE A:B:C switch, which - depending on your TAPE HEAD selection - will vary your delay speed in either an single octave up/down or changing delay time from your selection to a dotted version.

Noteworthy attributes of Strymon's El Capistan: Playable

Figure 2. Strymon Engineering's El Capistan, contemporary digital tape delay.

delay time knob; Small form factor, stomp box size; Dual purpose knobs, access secondary parameters by holding TAP + BYPASS; Various types of modulation and filters in feedback path; Delay time double or dot, depending on delay mode (TAPE HEAD); Single, Multiple or Fixed TAPE HEAD possible, for true tape emulation; Spring reverb can be added to output after feedback path [2]. Challenges of El Capistan: Unable to set modulation rate, limited ways to set modulation depth, one-preset save functionality with Strymon Switch hardware extension.

1.1.2 Roland SDE-2500 - released 1985

There is no arguing about the sound characteristics of the Roland SDE-2500 (and SDE-3000) delay units. Dub, reggae, surf music and many other genres have utilised the sonic wonders and still do. The unit delivers very low delay times, so it can function as a chorus or flanger effect. Speculations have been made as to how the old dub pioneers chained multiple delay units in order to 'insert' a chorus or flanger in their effect signal chain. When used together with a mixing desk, this delay is usually feeding back to itself via an aux or bus on the mixing desk, not utilizing the internal feedback mechanism. The unit is programmed from the front panel.

Noteworthy attributes of Roland SDE-2500: Very short delay times, down to flanger / chorus rate; Beautiful input stage distortion with volume meter LEDs; Modulation rate and depth knobs; Delay time double, single octave up button; Delay phase and filter bypass buttons; MIDI capable (preset recall via Program Change); Can save and restore settings as presets (e.g. a flanger preset, a quarter-note preset at 70 BPM etc.), a preset consists of: Delay Time, Delay Output Level, Feedback Level, Modulation (Rate, Depth), and On/Off of Delay Range, Delay Phase and Delay Filter Switches. Writing a new delay setting will automatically erase the old one. Presets can be edited and copied to one of 64 available locations [3]. Challenges of Roland SDE-2500: Big and bulky, rack mount size, delay

time parameter only changeable in single unit increments (milliseconds) making it hard to manipulate and perform with on the fly.

2. DESIGN & IMPLEMENTATION

Creating a delay which is both performative and can act as a sound design tool and a playable chaotic sound generator called for strict design concepts. Great inspiration was taken from Tom Erbe's (Soundhack x Make Noise) Erbe-Verb and the creation thereof [4] along with Tom's YouTube lecture [5]. Considering ease of access to most crucial and performative parameters, the top row knobs are mapped for direct access and immediate interaction. Selected parameters are: Delay Time (1 - 1,000 ms), Feedback (0 - 200 %), Filter Frequency (20Hz - 20kHz), and Filter Q (0.8 - 4) (see fig. 4). Parametrization and mapping is tested, and tested again under much scrutiny in order to maximize joy of interaction with the device, adhering the words of Tom Erbe [5] and Daniel Overholt [6] [7]. The sound design aspect of the delay is accessible only via a push encoder and a menu system. On the right side of the delay, an arcade push button is installed (see fig. 1). On the top panel, an LED offers visual feedback of delay time as well as a OLED display which offers various visualizations of the inputs and outputs as well as giving access to the menu system. Design considerations took much inspiration from the wonderful DAFX compilation [8] as well as [9] [10] [11] [12]. In replicating the sonic characteristics of the Roland SDE-2500, the audio analysis and interaction was mostly done by ear, experimentation, and feeling. Specifically, the sonic quality of the distortion at the input stage and in the feedback path was sought after. The unit has a delay time switch (Time X 2), which selects a maximum delay buffer to either 350 ms or 750 ms. Interestingly, bandwidth analysis of each mode of the Time X 2 button showed a decrease in bandwidth from 17kHz at 350 ms maximum delay time to 8kHz at maximum delay time 750 ms. The complete circuit diagram of the device is printed on top of the unit (as was common in the 80s), which served for inspiration. It was out of the scope for this project to conduct further signal analysis, but it will be taken up for further investigation in order to implement emulation parameters.

2.1 Qualitative interviews with contemporary dub producers

Apart from personal experience and dreams about the perfect live performance delay, I interviewed three music producers and live performers; Kanan-I from Rockers Ark Studio¹, Mathias Engstrøm from Dub Across Borders² / Odd Harmonics³, and Jesper Svane from Cigno Sound⁴ / Rumkraft⁵. All interviewees are avid professional music producers and sound designers heavily influenced by dub, reggae, and contemporary bass music like jungle, drum

¹ https://www.instagram.com/rockersark_studio/

² https://www.instagram.com/dub_across_borders/

³ <https://www.facebook.com/Oddharmonics/>

⁴ <https://cignosound.dk/>

⁵ <https://rumkraft.dk>

Figure 3. Roland SDE-2500, vintage digital delay.

Figure 4. Daisy Dub Delay top view.

Figure 5. Daisy Dub Delay menu section controllable via push encoder.

and bass, and dubstep. They are expert users of both analog, digital, hardware, and software delays of all kinds. Topics included aesthetics and sonic characteristics of the delay effect, best use cases, interface design, layout, control, mapping, most-wished-for functions which already exist, and most-wished-for functions not available in any delay known to them. Many new ideas came about and just as many good ideas were confirmed, among the most noteworthy was; direct control of delay time, feedback, filter cutoff frequency and resonance, delay time and filter frequency modulation; the possibility to go from a clean delay to a dirty broken-sounding unit, controlling distortion and modulation effects; tap tempo and buffer freeze functionality; continuous incremental or decremental octave up and down push-buttons; randomization of parameters (all or selected parameters); feedback range from 0 to way-more-than 100 %; possibility to use the unit only as a filter (possible by setting delay time to minimum and feedback to 0 %); portable and battery or USB powered, tabletop form factor;

2.2 Interface

2.2.1 Controllable parameters (see fig. 4 & 5)

Direct control via knobs and buttons - performance aspect

Knob 1 (top left), Delay Time (1 - 1,000 ms); Knob 2, Feedback (0 - 200 %); Knob 3, Filter Frequency (20Hz - 20kHz); Knob 4, Filter Q (0.8 - 4); Arcade push button (right side), Tap Tempo (multiple consecutive taps) or Freezing the Delay Buffer (hold arcade push button, freeze until release). See figure 4.

Controlled via menu and encoder - sound design aspect

Global dry/wet; Distortion amount (dry/wet); Distortion waveshape; Filter amount (dry/wet) on input and in feedback loop; Filter type - Lowpass, Highpass, Bandpass, Notch; Flanger bandwidth, center frequency, mod rate, amount (dry/wet), feedback; Delay time modulation speed via LFO; Delay time modulation LFO waveform (sine, sawtooth, square); Delay time modulation amount / depth of LFO. See figure 5.

2.3 Hardware

Daisy Seed embedded platform for music: ARM Cortex-M7 MCU, High fidelity AKM stereo audio codec with up to 24-bit 192kHz, 64MB of SDRAM, and 8MB of flash memory; 4 x 10k potentiometers; 1.3 inch SPI I2C Serial 128X64 OLED LCD Display Module; Rotary encoder 12mm with keyswitch (for controlling menu items); LED for visual delay time; Arcade style push button for freeze effect and tempo tap; Mono and stereo jacks for input / output; Cardboard box for enclosure;

2.4 Software

The Daisy Toolchain is a package by Electrosmith which contains the necessary tools to develop and flash custom software to the Daisy Seed microprocessor. How you decide to develop your software is versatile and can take many routes. For this project, Max and Gen was chosen since the author has prior knowledge working with those environments. Alternatives are the free and open-source PureData software, which can also be exported to Daisy Seed or bypassing any translational software and writing the code directly in C++.

Daisy Toolchain⁶ [13] - Git, Make, Arm Toolchain, dfu-util; DaisySP - A Powerful, Open Source DSP Library in C++ [13]; libdaisy - Hardware Library for the Daisy Audio Platform [13]; Max 8.1.11 (64 bit); Oopsy Max object

⁶ Daisy Toolchain on Github

Figure 6. Schematic for early Daisy Seed tape delay prototype - without tempo LED and arcade push button.

- gen~ to Daisy: exporting Max Gen patchers for the ElectroSmith Daisy hardware platforms; Visual Studio Code.

2.5 Procedure

Daisy Seed is the stand-alone microprocessor which costs around \$30. It is possible to build and prototype audio effects, synthesizers, and other DSP projects requiring real-time processing of audio with low latency. The capability of compiling and flashing gen~ patchers directly to the microprocessor makes a great prototyping platform for high-fidelity DSP projects, while also being able to run C++ code for further project iterations and coding adventures.

The following features are implemented and functional in a Max patch when executed in Max on a computer: 64-bit 92kHz stereo circular buffer delay with two [data] arrays as audio buffers, parametric delay time with smooth shifting of audio buffer playback speed and pitch, delay time modulation speed / amount / waveform, input stage and feedback path state variable filter cutoff / resonance / mix, flanger in feedback path with center frequency / bandwidth / rate / feedback, wave-shape distortion in feedback path with amount, subtle or aggressive injection of random noise to each delay buffer (for that gritty 70s sound). See fig. 9 on the very last page for an overview of the input, output and feedback path in the Max patch.

3. MAPPING

Initial parametrization and mapping is tested out on an iPad using mira.frame which allows direct and live multi-touch control of Max patches (see fig. 8). Various parameters are tested for functionality and importance, then scaled accordingly (exponentially using the Max and Gen objects [vexprpow(\$f1, 4)] and [scale0.1.0.10.]) or linearly when needed. The exponential example scales the control of the modulation amount, multiplying the modulation frequency with a 64bit floating point number between 0 and 10 with an exponent of 4. This results in good

Delay flow chart

Figure 7. Delay flow chart (N.B. input stage filter missing on figure).

control of the lower range of the modulation amount: the multiplication from 0 to 1 out of 10, for fine tuning your modulation amount [14]. Porting the patch to Daisy Seed gave rise to initial tweaking of parameters, among others scaling the filter frequency knob to Log Base 10 instead of linear. This was done by setting the full range of the frequency knob to a minimum of 20 Hz and maximum of 20,000 Hz. Afterwards, this is scaled to linear MIDI values between 21 and 127, and then converted back to frequencies with the object MTOF (MIDI To Frequency) - with the result being logarithmic. The final output is then linearly interpolated with the object [slide] with a timing of samplerate / 100. It functions and sounds great, so all linear to logarithmic functions is done in this way throughout the project.

4. DISCUSSION

Porting Max patches with gen~ objects to Daisy Seed presented some challenges. The first version of the tape-style circular buffer delay used the [buffer] object which has to be referenced outside (top level) of the gen~ patcher (one level higher than the Oopsy object allows porting). This is impossible to compile to Daisy Seed, so the [data] object is used instead. Another crucial problem is disparate handling of floating point numbers between Max / Gen and Daisy Seed. Gen handles floating point numbers as 64bit, Daisy Seed handles floating point numbers as 32bit. This resulted in audible artifacts when using a phasor (upwards

Figure 8. Gen delay presentation mode in Max with MIRA frame controllable via iPad.

sawtooth waveform oscillator) to index the read-and-write position of the `[data]` buffer: scanning through the buffer from sample 1 to length-of-buffer with a rising phasor. The solution to the rounding errors is to use a `[counter]` object which indexes upwards in a specific step size (i.e. one sample) over the length of the `[data]` buffer, instead of an oscillator indexing at audio rate.

The delay sounds great and behaves as you would expect once you know the knobs and menu system. Usability testing showed promising results for both the performance and the sound design aspect. Generally, every user who tried the delay was happy and impressed with the sound quality, interaction, and the visual OLED display and arcade button. A good deal of bugs got squashed during the qualitative usability tests, parameters got tweaked, and new features appeared on the drawing board.

Wish-list for future implementation: More modulation effects in feedback path; phaser, chorus; Compression at output stage; Randomize all parameters (kick the can!); Multi tap / head mode; amount of taps (will automatically spread time of taps in time related to the harmonic series, e.g. octaves, minor/major thirds, fifths etc.); Double or half the delay time to octave shift sound in buffer.

Acknowledgments

A big thanks goes out to the participants' who helped evaluate and partake in qualitative interviews. Another goes out to my professor Daniel Overholt and to the always helpful and friendly Silvin Willemsen (AAU, SMC) and Archelaos Vasileiou (bluefxdevices.com)

5. REFERENCES

- [1] L. Bradley, *This is reggae music: the story of Jamaica's music*. Grove Press.
- [2] Strymon dtape technology - white paper. [Online]. Available: <https://www.strymon.net/strymon-dtape-technology-white-paper/>
- [3] Roland, *Digital Delay SDE-2500 Owner's Manual*, Roland.
- [4] T. Erbe, "Building the erbe-verb: Extending the feedback delay network reverb for modular synthesizer use," p. 4.
- [5] —, "Tom erbe / soundhack "designing the make noise erbe-verb" reverb design lecture," https://youtu.be/II_qdtQKnqk?t=660, December 2019.
- [6] D. J. Overholt, "Musical interface technology: Multimodal control of multidimensional parameter spaces for electroacoustic music performance."
- [7] D. Overholt, "The musical interface technology design space," vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 217–226. [Online]. Available: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S1355771809000326/type/journal_article
- [8] U. Zölzer, Ed., *DAFX: Digital Audio Effects: Zölzer/DAFX: Digital Audio Effects*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. [Online]. Available: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1002/9781119991298>
- [9] W. C. Pirkle, *Designing audio effect plugins in C++: for AAX, AU, and VST3 with DSP theory*, second edition ed. Routledge.
- [10] V. J. Manzo, *Max/MSP/Jitter for music: a practical guide to developing interactive music systems for education and more*, second edition ed. Oxford University Press.
- [11] A. Cipriani and M. Giri, *Electronic music and sound design. Volume 1*, fourth edition ed. ConTempoNet.
- [12] —, *Electronic music and sound design. Volume 2*, third edition ed. ConTempoNet.
- [13] Electrosmith GitHub. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/electro-smith>
- [14] M. Puckette, "The theory and technique of electronic music.pdf."

Figure 9. gen~ patch overview.